

Best-fitting models

We present the FASTWIND best-fitting models to the observed spectra for the Cygnus OB2 O-type population analyzed in the article *Spectroscopic analysis of the known O population in Cygnus OB2* (Berlanas et al. 2020, A&A, in press). The observed spectra (in black) is overplotted to the best-fitting model (in red) resulting from the *iacob-gbat* analysis. Each star is labeled with its name and the model. He I, He II and H lines are indicated with solid, dashed and dotted short vertical lines, respectively.

